

Lexicon de Plantas (Lexicon of Plants)

Cyclicity and Participatory Community Experience in an Immersive Animated Installation

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ABSTRACT

Lexicon de Plantas (2024) is a large-scale audiovisual and site-specific art installation that immerses the observer in a realm of visual poetry through layering memories from the past with contemplation of the present and of possible futures. It features the transformation of drawings into animations; these are then projected onto paper sculptures. It features conceptual and collaborative activations that work to break down the barriers between artist and audience by sharing community-sourced stories relating to memories of plants. This work invites the audience to engage with the complexities of memory, migration, and belonging. It explores magical realism through a lens of belonging and mutual compassion as key parts of collective wellness. The goal is to inspire environmental awareness through acts of care and intentionality by remembering and revering shared familial traditions that link to our relationships with plants. These memories become heirlooms, manifested in a space that allows for reflection before passing them down. The end of the installation featured a live music performance, readings of the written memories, and an open invitation for the audience to participate by telling their stories related to memories of plants. This collaboration between interdisciplinary visual artist Alejandra Abad and musician Steve Jones aims to foster empathy and to nurture our communities by engaging memory in relation to the moving image, collective awareness, and storytelling.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Artistic Animation • Site-Specific Installation • Performance • Audiovisuality • Digital Arts • Magical Realism • Environmental Futures

KEYWORDS

Art, Performance, Plants, Socially Engaged Art Practice, Community, Collaboration, Memories, Ecology, Sustainability

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1 POEM BACKGROUND: *ILUSIONES*, 1949

The starting point for this project was developing a visual interpretation of a poem type written in Caracas in 1949 by Jose Colmenares, Alejandra's Venezuelan grandfather, who was an educator and an advocate for nature. This primary source material acts as a key to the door of memories. The poem creates a sense of veneration and remembrance for the past while exploring the significance of reclaiming memory in the present. While memories of immigrants often assimilate to the promise of modernity, this also carries the possibility of erasure, trauma, and the exploitation of both land and a body of immigrant stories as new communities need to make sense of a new land. The poem *Ilusiones* responds to life in Caracas, a buzzing city given the economic growth of Venezuela in the 1940s, by reminding the audience that any perceived or real gains can be illusory or temporary. By being aware of the dual traumas related to the human body and to natural bodies, we can diagnose and work towards collective treatment of social ills.

To understand why immigrants would leave their beloved homeland, it is necessary to understand how displacement connects to forced dislocation from the environment. "The first oil well exploited for industrial production was Zumaque I/Mene Grande, roughly fifty miles south from Cabimas, claimed in 1914 by Caribbean Petroleum (later acquired by Royal Dutch Shell). However, it was not until the 1922 explosion of Barroso II (also known as Los Barrosos) near Cabimas that Venezuela gained widespread attention as one of the most fertile lands for oil-exploitation in the world" (Barrios 50). *Ilusiones* presents a disillusion with industrial modernity, instead offering admiration for the beauty of our natural world.

Alejandra's own historical and familial background informs *Lexicon de Plantas*, which in turn relates to many immigrant experiences from around the area of the exhibition. Florida is an international hub of memories tied to the land and ancestral

knowledge of communities who also share links to a past in another part of the world. This work suggests that as we enter an age of climate crisis, we need to remember those temporal and familial connections if we are to invoke love and care for the environment and for one another. The video sequences in the exhibit show how animation in particular is a realm of hope. Stop-motion animation is the union of the machine and the hand, as is visual music; conceptualizing future possibilities rooted in the experience of the physical body allows for transcendence through the concrete illusion of animation that blends science and the artist's hand. As the animation cycles, it fragments into abstraction while accompanied by soundscapes, drawings, and digital reproduction of the text of the poem *Ilusiones*.

Figure 1: *Lexicon de Plantas, 2024*

2 INSTALLATION

The audiovisual installation contains various interpretations of memory through animated cycles and musical composition. The space opens with a laser-cut version of the poem *Ilusiones*, which appears floating in the center of the space. The original poem was digitally scanned then vectorized to be laser-cut onto velum paper; the gaps for the letters allow light to come through openings that reveal the textures of the animated projection on the back wall. The physical poem floats in front of the looping text of the poem, creating a mask with the solid paper and the open cut-outs of the letters. The installation features three different projections on each wall. On the main wall is an interpretation of the poem, titled *Visual Poem: Ilusiones* (2024), which combines text and animations using hand-drawn elements and laser-cut objects; after 2:07 minutes it incorporates the physical manifestation of the original typewritten poem through text that is displayed alongside iterations of animated motifs based on paper cutouts of the forms from the sculptures on the sides of the space. The left wall features hand-cut shapes in a layered paper sculpture that cascades in front of a second animated projection; this animation is called

Flora (2024) and contains paper-cut color pencil drawings made into a stop-motion animation. This section emphasizes the ephemeral nature of creation and uses nine drawings that refer to the memories of plants from Alejandra's grandfather's garden. This video loops after 2:07 minutes and deconstructs the cycles of hand-drawn memories, recomposing constituent elements into new forms in a manner that mirrors the cyclical processes of nature: i.e. the natural world transforms into drawings, and then the drawings transform into animations. These drawings are cut, rearranged, edited, and then projected onto the onto 20-foot-tall hand-cut hanging paper cultures. Each transformation and (re)iteration combine to make new imagined shapes, and these forms in turn prompt ideations of a new and hopeful symbology. The third wall features a video titled *Memorias* (2024), which features projections of community-sourced memories that are related to plants (discussed in further detail in Section 4 below).

Figure 2: *Animation Projected onto Hand-Cut Hanging Paper*

3 MUSIC & SOUND COLLABORATION

The soundscape accompanies the main visual poem in the center projection (Fig. 3). As the animation cycles, it fragments into abstraction while accompanied by soundscapes and a narration of the poem *Ilusiones*. The musical score by Steve Jones followed prompts from Alejandra; these include using Alejandra's grandfather's cuatro (a four-stringed instrument from Venezuela), which elevates the personal sentiment, nostalgia, and sense of reverence in the work, along with the inclusion of specific sounds of nature that would be familiar and instantly recognizable to Venezuelans to invoke Proustian memories of association. Genre-wise, the score participates in folk traditions that elevate the memories and experiences of the common people. Venezuelans regard the cuatro as the national instrument of the country. The sound immediately evokes a sense of reverence for both human

workers and their relationship to nature in the listener, given the cuatro's central place in the folk music of the country. Other sound elements include textural synthesizers and field recordings of singing coquis (frogs) and various birds to create a lush and vibrant atmosphere brimming with life. This fusion of visual and audio elements immerses the audience in the complexities of memory, migration, belonging, and the dynamic interplay between art and nature. Each of these elements invite the audience to reconnect with the environment. The sound mirrors the visual progression and tempo of the animation. For the one-off live performance (addressed in Section 5 below), Steve and Alejandra layered in live instruments and vocals over the installation's soundtrack that continued to play in the background. This created a unique and welcoming environment for participation, consciously elevating the audience in solidarity with the folk underpinnings of the musical score.

Figure 3: Stop-Motion Animated Paper Shapes

4 PARTICIPATORY ART COMPONENT

Visitors could access a complementary zine that contains the poem *Ilusiones* as well as a QR code with an invitation to share their own memories related to plants; an extended label on the left wall also displayed this same QR code. The prompt simply read, "What is your memory related to plants?" (Fig. 2). Participants used their mobile phones to share their memories over four months, which was the duration of the exhibition at the gallery.

Figure 4: Projection of Shared Memories

The shared memories from the community were then projected on the right wall (Fig. 4). At the end of every two-week period, the gallery would update the video to add the newly received memories which would loop in the projection between the paper sculptures. These stories explore belonging and agency as the audience shared their memories, experience, and at times reimagined environments. The two large-scale paper sculptures contained reconstructed elements of the original drawings to create a new iteration of symbology; the resulting shapes and forms reflect the main animation in a new context, mirroring the way memory works both individually and culturally within the visual context of layering, abstraction, and light.

5 LIVE PERFORMANCE & PARTICIPATION

The installation was on view from February 8 to May 18, 2024. On the closing day, Alejandra read selected memories from the community, and joined in a live musical soundscape composition by collaborating musician Steve Jones. At the end of the performance, the audience was invited to share additional memories related to plants. This activation provided a space for reflection and connection where people could listen and share via familial remembrance, and then continue to connect with one another after the performance. This project opened the possibility of ideation for new environmental futures that center folk storytelling. Stories ranged from expressions of grief to appreciation of both our relationship with the environment and also of our ties to those who came before us. Many of the shared stories centered around grandparents who imparted generational wisdom regarding how to maintain connection with nature.

Figure 5: Audience Member Sharing Memories

6 AESTHETIC CONTEXT & INFLUENCES

A significant influence on the animation process in this project is Oskar Fischinger's *Optical Poem* (1938). His modernist style incorporated paper shapes and visual music. Alejandra's work builds on his pioneering use of paper shapes, cut-outs, and abstraction, while adding the new content of communal memory to extend a link between the past, the present, and imagined futures.

Olafur Eliasson's work engages in utilizing space, light, and participation from the viewer. For example, *The Weather Project* (2003) is a large-scale installation that actively invites the public to experience the illusion of the sun inside the Turbine Hall at the Tate Modern. This site-specific installation invites people to conceptualize the boundaries between humans, nature, and technology.

William Kentridge's work is formally influential in terms of transforming drawings into animation, and content-wise as his animations make political and social commentaries related to power structures and memory (e.g. *Johannesburg, the 2nd Greatest City After Paris* from 1989).

Finally, Barbara Kruger uses the language of advertising to pull the viewer into her immersive installation at the MoMA, *Thinking of You. I Mean Me. I Mean You*. This piece expands the awareness of language's social impact via repetition of written words in a gigantic space that draws attention to the presence of the audience within it. Alejandra's work provides an alternative to consumption through the act of remembering our symbiotic relationships to plants, while adding a more direct and active participatory element.

7 CONCLUSION & IMPLICATIONS

In her future work Alejandra intends to use processing to code projections that can interpret a database of memories to update the projections of newly shared stories in real time. It was a challenge to keep up with the gallery when regularly sending files to make sure that new memories could be successfully added.

Continuing this work is particularly important now, since sharing familial memories during a political shift towards xenophobia against immigration can build connection to one another globally. Revisiting common memories can be a key part of the healing

process as we often suffer from erasure and contested colonial histories.

Plans going forward involve applying to the Knight Foundation Grant and other funding opportunities to further expand the reach of this project. The goals of connection and belonging are important political actions, hence the intention of continuing to make art that elevates people, immigrant stories, and the environment with which we all need to coexist.

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